

PREDICTION OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES USING A HOMOGENIZATION PROCEDURE

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Abstract

This paper presents a numerical method to compute the elastic properties of a resin impregnated wire mesh based on homogenization theory. Due to the locally rather complicated geometry the equations of elasticity cannot be solved in closed form. The finite element method is used to solve the local problem and the resulting over-determined system of equations for the material parameters is solved in the least square sense. A parametric study into the effect of the design parameters wire spacing and wire diameter on the overall properties is conducted

1 Introduction

It is common practice to reinforce resin based materials through incorporation of woven fabrics or wire meshes thus producing materials featuring desirable properties like high strength, low weight and low cost. The homogenization method has been applied to such materials in the past to compute their mechanical and thermal properties [1] [2]. The main advantage of this method as compared to experimental procedures is the fact that the effect of a change in the design of the material - be it the arrangement of the reinforcement or the properties of the components - can be studied at relatively low cost thus providing a possibility to optimize the composite material for a particular application.

In the present study, the underlying engineering application concerns directly bonded orthodontic brackets. Traditionally these brackets are made of stainless steel and consist of two distinct parts, the body of the bracket and the bracket-base which are assembled through brazing or electro-resistance welding, see Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The body of the bracket is either machined from a block of metal or cast to relatively high degree of accuracy to guarantee the success of the orthodontic treatment.

Figure 1: Orthodontic bracket.

The bracket base serves the sole purpose of creating a reliable link between the body of the bracket and the tooth. It consists of a wire mesh backed by a thin metal foil. One of the main features of this design is a low bending stiffness. Consequently the margin of the adhesive interface between the bracket and the tooth with its inherent risk of fracture is mostly unloaded. During the bonding process, an adhesive resin - generally a polymeric resin filled with glass-particles - flows into the voids of the mesh where it hardens, thus creating a mechanical lock. The wire-mesh hence doesn't serve primarily the classical purpose of reinforcing the resin but it achieves a structural link between dissimilar materials.

In order to understand the influence of the layout of the wire mesh on the stress field of the bracket base a numerical model of the system bracket-adhesive-tooth is constructed. It is clear that an exact representation of the resin impregnated wire mesh is beyond the reach of even advanced engineering computation facilities. Therefore this layer is treated like a composite material with a set of overall, homogeneous properties. These properties are computed by means of an homogenization procedure.

2 Homogenization

As the word suggests, a homogenization procedure is a mathematical method which transforms a heterogeneous material into a homogeneous continuum which exhibits equivalent material behaviour on a macroscopic level. Obviously a certain amount of the information about local (microscopic) occurrences is lost. Only a brief outline of the results of homogenization theory upon which this investigation is based is given here. For a more detailed account see for example [3] or [4].

The homogenization theory makes two assumptions with regards to the heterogeneous material -also termed the micro structure - it is applied to. Firstly it is assumed that the scale of the micro-structure is small compared to the overall dimensions of the problem. This entails that the local strain ϵ_{local} is separable into the global strain observed on a macroscopic level ϵ_{app} and a local perturbation ϵ^* due to the inhomogeneities.

$$\epsilon_{local} = \epsilon_{app} + \epsilon^* \quad (1)$$

Secondly it is assumed that the micro-structure is locally periodic, i.e. it consists of self-repeating units, the unit-cells. This assumption is the warrant for the validity of the computations performed on a unit-cell through-out the structure.

Under these assumption the apparent stiffness matrix, that is the constitutive law of an homogeneous material which has the same macroscopic properties as the heterogeneous composite can be defined through the equation

$$\sigma_{app} = \mathbf{C}_{app} \epsilon_{app} \quad (2)$$

where ϵ_{app} and σ_{app} are the volume average of the strain and the stress over a unit cell. In most cases it will be quite impossible to compute the stresses and the strains for the unit cell in closed form. In practice, a numerical procedure like the finite element method can be used to solve the governing differential equations - the equations of elasticity in this case.

With regards to the boundary conditions employed when computing the stresses and strains on the unit cell two restrictions apply. Firstly the displacements have to be such that neither gaps nor overlapping between neighbouring unit cells occurs. It follows from the periodicity of the micro-structure that this is equivalent to equal displacements on opposing surfaces of the unit cell (plus a rigid body movement). In other words, the strain field has to be periodic. Secondly, the traction vector along the border of the unit cell has to be in equilibrium with the neighbouring cell. The periodicity of the micro-structure entails that the traction has to be of equal magnitude and acting in opposite directions on opposing faces of the unit cell.

3 Numerical Procedure

The unit cell in the case of the resin impregnated wire mesh is one square of the mesh as shown in Fig. 2: the global mesh can be constructed by flipping the unit cell about one of its axes and translating it by its own length. The choice of the unit cell is in as much arbitrary as any part of the whole mesh with the same dimensions would serve the same purpose regardless of the location and orientation of the wires. However, this particular choice allows an easy implementation of the restriction regarding the boundary conditions. It also turns out to be very convenient during the construction of the finite element mesh.

The wires are modelled as prismatic bars with circular cross-section and their shape is approximated by a sin function. The wires run parallel and at right angle respectively and they are rigidly connected at the crossing points. In accordance with information obtained from a manufacturer the squashing of the mesh due to the electro-resistance welding process was set to 25%, i.e. the thickness of the mesh is 1.5 times the wire diameter. For simplicity this squashing was modeled as an inter-penetration of the wires at the crossing points and a flattening at the top and the bottom surface, that is the wires retain their circular cross-section and the material that in practice is displaced within the wire trough plastic flow is removed from the model.

This model of the wire together with the matching resin negative is discretized using the standard mesh generator Patran (Version 1.3-1). Because of the rather tangled geometry an unstructured mesh generation algorithm leading to tetrahedral elements is chosen. To counteract the inaccuracy generally associated with tetrahedral elements a relatively fine discretization is chosen, see Fig. 3.

In order to satisfy the restrictions placed on the boundary conditions the loads are applied through imposed displacements. In this way the periodicity of the strain-field can be enforced exactly while the equilibrium condition is only approximately full-filled. However the particular choice made for the unit cell (the fact that it is point-symmetric about its center) entails a natural compliance of the surface tractions with the equilibrium condition.

Up to this point, no assumption concerning the directionality of the over-all material behaviour of the composite have been made. Consequently there are 21 constants describing

Figure 2: Wire mesh at the bracket base (computer model) with the unit cell isolated on the right.

the constitutive relation to be identified, requiring a huge computational effort. It is common practice to reduce this effort by taking clues from the structural geometry as to the qualitative material behaviour of the composite. In the present case it was decided to use a transversally isotropic model. The behaviour of this model is fully described by 6 independent constants. Choosing the coordinate system so as to coincide with the principal axes of the material leads to mutual un-coupling of the shear deformations as well as to un-coupling of the shear and extensional modes of deformation; however, the three extensions remain coupled. The constitutive equation takes the form

$$\sigma_{app} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{21} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{31} & C_{32} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \epsilon_{app} \quad (3)$$

Choosing the direction 1 and 2 to be the 'in-plane' directions while direction 3 is the out-of-plane direction the following relations exist between the elements of the matrix C

$$C_{11} = C_{22} \quad C_{13} = C_{23} \quad C_{55} = C_{66} \quad (4)$$

Furthermore, the matrix C is symmetric.

Application of any particular state of strain in the above equation with all components non-zero provides 6 scalar equations for the six independent constants of the constitutive matrix C . However the four constants associated with the normal modes of deformation appear in only three of these equations. It is hence necessary to apply a second state of strain which is linearly independent from the first. This generates a further six equations thus producing an over-determined system of equations for the material constants. This system has to be solved in the least square sense.

Figure 3: Finite element mesh of the unit cell: reinforcing wires on the right and matching resin cast on the left.

The elements of the compliance matrix C are linked to the technical constants by the following relations:

$$C_{11} = \frac{1}{E_x} \quad C_{33} = \frac{1}{E_z} \quad C_{12} = -\frac{\nu_{yx}}{E_x} \quad C_{13} = -\frac{\nu_{zx}}{E_x} \quad C_{44} = \frac{1}{G_{xy}} \quad C_{66} = \frac{1}{G_{zx}} \quad (5)$$

As stated above, the loads are applied through imposed displacements. In order to generate the two linearly independent states of strain the following two sets of displacements are imposed in the finite element computation:

Case 1:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \|x\| = x_0 & u = 0.01 * x \\ \|y\| = y_0 & v = 0 \\ \|z\| = z_0 & w = 0 \end{array} \quad \text{plus} \quad \begin{array}{ll} \|x\| = x_0 & u = 0.01 * z \\ \|y\| = y_0 & v = 0 \\ \|z\| = z_0 & u = 0.01 * z \\ & w = 0 \end{array}$$

Case 2:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \|x\| = x_0 & u = 0 \\ \|y\| = y_0 & v = 0 \\ \|z\| = z_0 & w = 0.01 * z \end{array} \quad \text{plus} \quad \begin{array}{ll} \|x\| = x_0 & u = 0.01 * y \\ \|y\| = y_0 & v = 0 \\ & u = 0.01 * y \\ \|z\| = z_0 & w = 0 \end{array}$$

The variables u , v and w stand for the displacements in x , y and z direction. The unit cell is assumed to be centred at the origin of a cartesian system of coordinates and its dimensions are $2x_0$ by $2y_0$ by $2z_0$.

Table 1: Elastic properties of the constituent materials.

wire	E= 210000.0 MPa	$\nu=0.3$ (steel)
resin	E = 11721.0 MPa	$\nu=0.21$ (concise)

In this study, the wire diameter was varied between 75 and 200 μm while the spacing between wires covered the range from 200 to 750 μm . The wire material was stainless steel and the adhesive resin used was *Concise* (3M dental products). The properties of these materials are displayed in table 1. Linear elastic behaviour of both materials is assumed and the resin is perfectly bonded to the wires.

4 Results and discussion

The results obtained for the technical constants are displayed in table 2. In addition to the material parameters the table also shows the bending stiffness per unit width about the x-axis (which is equivalent to the bending stiffness about the y-axis) as defined by

$$K_{bend} = I_{xx}E_x \quad (6)$$

Table 2: Material constants and bending stiffness for various wire diameters and spacings.

diam [μm]	space [μm]	E_{xx} [MPa]	E_{zz} [MPa]	ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}	G_{xy} [MPa]	G_{xz} [MPa]	K_{bend} [N mm]
75.	200.	52706.3	46538.4	.147	.225	15895.4	19830.1	6.253
75.	300.	39200.1	30319.2	.126	.235	10146.5	14439.0	4.651
75.	400.	32256.5	24471.3	.128	.232	8335.8	11895.9	3.827
75.	500.	28007.5	20622.7	.132	.230	7324.8	10337.9	3.323
75.	750.	22935.1	17212.6	.151	.224	6184.0	8368.0	2.721
100.	200.	67920.1	62360.4	.177	.219	22809.8	25908.2	19.102
100.	300.	48147.4	39721.7	.136	.230	13382.7	17743.6	13.541
100.	400.	39151.3	30697.9	.125	.235	10066.9	14154.7	11.011
100.	500.	33918.3	25226.1	.125	.235	8477.1	12176.3	9.539
100.	750.	26441.4	19505.4	.134	.229	6887.7	9717.8	7.436
200.	200.	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>
200.	300.	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>	<i>n.a.</i>
200.	400.	67582.4	59605.5	.172	.223	21834.5	25327.4	152.060
200.	500.	55647.0	48565.0	.147	.227	16375.5	20562.3	125.205
200.	750.	41128.9	32326.9	.121	.238	10384.1	14630.5	92.54

The two Youngs moduli and shear moduli increase almost linearly with the volume fraction of the wire. As an example, the in-plane Youngs and shear modulus are shown in Fig. 4. In fact, the in-plane Youngs modulus can be estimated to within 7% using the basic theory for uniaxially reinforced composites. However, this theory yields none of the other material constants. It is also interesting to note that increasing the volume fraction of the wire through reducing the spacing or through increasing the wire diameter has the same effect on the Youngs and shear modulae.

The variation of the Poissons ratios with the volume fraction of the wire is displayed in Fig. 5. The behaviour of ν_{zx} - the constant which describes the reaction in x direction to a load applied in z direction - is quite readily explained: the wires, running in x and y direction, shield much less load from the resin in the out-of-plane direction leaving the resin to bear a major part of the stress. Consequently the matrix is rather heavily strained and the composites Poissons ratio is very close to the one of the resin. The biggest variation observed for ν_{zx} with the volume fraction of the wire is about 5%.

The behaviour of the other Poissons ratio, ν_{xy} is somewhat more interesting. This parameter quantifies the reaction of the material in y-direction to an excitation in x direction. For all the designs analysed ν_{xy} is below the Poissons ratio of both constituent materials. The curves for the thinner wires (75 and 100 μm) show a minimum at a wire-volume fraction of about 20 to 25% and it can be assumed that the same behaviour would occur for the thicker wires (200

Figure 4: In-plane Youngs and shear modulus as a function of the volume fraction of the wire for three different wire diameters.

Figure 5: Poissons ratios as a function of the volume fraction of the wire for three different wire diameters.

μ_m) if the investigated range would be extended. Structural arguments can be put forth to explain this behaviour. The main part of the in-plane load will be transferred through the wires much in the way the load is transferred in a truss, leaving the matrix largely unloaded. However, as the volume fraction of the wires becomes smaller more and more of the load will be transferred through the resin; the load transfer mechanism resembles more and more the one in a solid, which accounts for the rising Poisson's ratio towards small wire volume fractions. The same argument holds if the reinforcement is increased over a certain level. In this case the wires become bulkier and produce an increased Poisson effect in their own right. This behaviour is interesting in the sense that it shows that the composite can be optimized to minimize the in-plane transversal reaction to loading along the wire direction. Figure 6 shows the variation of the bending stiffness as defined in Eqn 6 with the volume fraction of the wire. Clearly the relation is linear. It is equally clear that the factor governing the bending stiffness is not the properties of the composite but its thickness. If the bracket base is to be kept flexible it is of prime importance to choose a thin wire and try to achieve any other desirable properties through adjusting of the spacing.

5 Conclusions

Homogenization theory was used to compute the material properties of a resin impregnated wire mesh. The influence of the wire thickness and the spacing on the properties of reinforced

Figure 6: Bending stiffness (per unit width) as a function of the volume fraction of the wire for three different wire diameters.

material were studied. The results show that the method can be used to study the influence of the design parameters on the properties of the final product without going to the length of prototype manufacturing.

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